

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BODY CONSCIOUSNESS LEVEL AND DIFFERENT DISCIPLINES AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Physical appearance is one of the first individual characteristics noticed by others. It cause body consciousness among individuals and their perception depends on other's view. In today's culture adults closely related to a drive of thinness Body image dissatisfaction, weight concern, eating problem, have become especially significant issues on college campuses, Universities with up to 90% of students reporting that they worry about body image. Different programs and university environment influences their perceptions and cause high level of objectified body consciousness.

Objectives: To assess the relationship between body consciousness level and educational programs among undergraduate students.

Material and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 287 students at New Campus of People University of Medical and Health Science for Women Nawabshah, All allied health science programs were included under the age group of 19 to 28 years with the consent of the students, Data were collected using a structured Scale based questionnaire and analyzed by SPSS version 25. Frequency, Percentage, Mean, SE, SD and correlation test were applied to analyze the relationship.

Results: The mean age of students was 21.6 ± 1.535 Years. Program status of the student from demographic information was significantly associated with negative correlation OBCS p-value < 0.05 with $r = -.124$. Most of the students 207(73.9%) had high level of body consciousness and 23.6% had a moderate level and only 7(2.5%) were in low level. It has three subscales; Surveillance mean 33.98 high surveillance include how a person stays occupied with their body , performs body checking behaviors and looks at their body from an observer's. The body shame mean 33.41 the high mean value specify the embarrassment a student feel for not fulfilling the ideal body standards, control belief score mean 32. this subscale explain the degree of perceived control a person has on her appearance, high mean indicate that students have a strong belief that their appearance can be controlled by putting efforts.

Conclusion: Findings of this study concluded that education programs influences the perceptions of the students regarding their body image and cause

consciousness about the looks. It can be harmful if adults have highly over conscious. So, counseling, teaching and discussion about body consciousness and its impact on body and healthy lifestyle habits helps to control objectified body consciousness level and encourage adults to involve themselves in physical activities, sessions to develop self-confidence and self-worth.

INTRODUCTION

Every person has a unique and varied body shape or physical appearance. Physical appearance is one of the first individual characteristics noticed by others and has an impact on their social interactions; dissatisfaction with one's body image is a common experience for many individuals expressing direct approval or disapproval of other's body image in the media and their surroundings. Body shaming is an insulting act by commenting on people's body image or appearance or shape that hurts the feeling of individuals and given an impact on their mental health which results in the person becoming less-confident. It is form of criticism conducting by community members, including those who are close to such adults' family members, friends, colleagues and their surroundings.

Adulthood is a critical period of transition between childhood and adulthood, which is depend on significant changes in the body, mind and emotions, well-being.

An important part in the mindset of the youths body image according to the study females are more body conscious and concerned than male about their looks, beauty and their body shape that's why female face more criticism than males, Young adults who experienced body shaming or continuously have experience body objectification worry about their appearance and trying to cut out or not facing the society/environment. As a results victims of the body objectification tend to experience higher level of insecurities, loneliness, unhappiness and low self-worth due to the experienced of being bullied. Up to 90% of students reporting that they worry about body image the pressure to achieve high standards thinness, attractiveness, body shape in a competitive college environment is related to lower self-assurance. Body objectification for females often focuses on physical features like weight, body shape, and skin color, driven by beauty ideals of thinness and fair skin, this often

results in self-objectification, where women feel they are not "adequate" if they fail to meet beauty standards.

A cross sectional study was conducted in various departments of the Bucharest Economic Studies Academy (ESA) results revealed that 79% girls were dissatisfied with their bodies only 21% were happy with their body size and shape. Another survey data was collected from 50 respondents ranged from ages 13 to 25 and the result revealed that only 48% of participants felt positive about their body and the overall 52% participants felt why discontent with their appearance. And the survey based study design conducted about the awareness of the impact of body shaming in Malaysia among the students of university(MARA Melaka Branch) and results concluded that 68% participants felt angry/sad or frustrated about it, 32% were able to accept body statement.

Cross-cultural research involving 2165 adults from four European countries(United Kingdom, Italy Poland, Romania and Iran), found that self objectification, operationalized through body shame and body surveillance, varies, where media internalization and socio cultural factors shape OBCS differently but consistently contribute to negative body perceptions and diminished self-respect. In Pakistan from different universities and medical colleges such as NUST, NMU, RMU, CMH Lahore and Quetta, AMC Rawalpindi, NUML, GIKI, UVAS, UOS and other universities results revealed that more than half of the participants have pressure and more conscious about body 57% students reporting have good body image satisfaction and 43% have reported body image dissatisfaction. A study of 561 university students found that females exhibited greater levels of body consciousness, A large proportion of Pakistani young adults from roughly 50% to 60% depending on the measure experience elevated body dissatisfaction, objectified body

consciousness, and related psychological distress, especially among females in urban areas.

Objectified Body consciousness caused by body shaming and it is an act of insulting other person's body and a way of criticizing individual about their body shape, size, and appearance. Young adults, who are moving towards their new phase of life and go through the educational environment, are very concern about their self and more sensitive because of their appearance among the other students. Body consciousness is very harmful for students or young adults because in their adulthood period they are building their physical health, confidence, self-identity develops their personality and going through different educational disciplines, while objectified body consciousness make them to occupied themselves and loss their self-value and feel insecure, loss their interest in their studies, depressed and anxious about their beauty standards which affect their daily life routine. Therefore, this study designed to evaluate the relationship between body consciousness and different disciplines among undergraduate students and the findings may highlight how the different educational disciplines and students perceptions associate with their body consciousness level.

RESULTS

MATERIAL & METHODS

This study is a descriptive cross-relational study used to evaluate the relationship between objectified body consciousness and different disciplines among undergraduate students with the use of structured based Questionnaire OBCS scale. This study was conducted in People's University Of Medical And Health Sciences For Women Shaheed Benazir Abad New Campus in all Allied health science programs. Data collection was over two months of period of time from 17 November to 17 January 2026 after approval of IRB (Institutional Review Board) of PUMHSW. Sample size was 287 calculated by Yamane Formula with 95% confidence level and 5% of margin error. A purposive non probability sampling technique was used to select participants. In inclusion criteria Participants were included in the study are students of BS Nursing, BSPH, DPT, and Pharmacy-D in PUMHSW SBA and Participants aged between 19 and 28 only Female students. Exclusion criteria included those who do not want to participate and students who are not studying in Allied Health program in new campus of PUMHSW e.g.: MBBS, physiology, Cardiology and others.

Figure No1: Age of the Participants

Table 1: OBCS score in Frequency and Percentage

Questions	SD	D	SWD	N	SWA	A	SA
Q1	103(36.8%)	34(12.1%)	16(5.7%)	38(13.6%)	29(10.4%)	40(14.3%)	20(7.1%)
Q2	97(34.6%)	32(11.4%)	23(8.2%)	19(6.8%)	19(6.8%)	59(21.1%)	31(11.1%)
Q3	81(28.9%)	24(8.6%)	31(11.1%)	27(9.6%)	35(12.5%)	62(22.1%)	20(7.1%)
Q4	61(21.8%)	44(15.7%)	26(9.3%)	38(13.6%)	34(12.1%)	56(20.0%)	21(7.5%)
Q5	58(20.7%)	40(14.3%)	28(10.0%)	36(12.9%)	44(15.7%)	52(18.6%)	22(7.9%)
Q6	62(22.1%)	33(11.8%)	14(5.0%)	24(8.6%)	53(18.9%)	66(23.6%)	28(10.0%)
Q7	43(15.4%)	33(11.8%)	22(7.9%)	38(13.6%)	43(15.4%)	69(24.6%)	32(11.4%)
Q8	49(17.5%)	42(15.0%)	33(11.8%)	23(8.2%)	32(11.4%)	60(21.4%)	41(14.6%)

Table 2: OBCS score in frequency and percentage

Questions	SD	D	SWD	N	SWA	A	SA
Q9	54(19.3%)	57(20.4%)	19(6.8%)	29(10.4%)	26(9.3%)	50(17.9%)	45(16.1%)
Q10	48(17.1%)	59(21.1%)	19(6.8%)	36(12.9%)	36(12.9%)	42(15.0%)	40(14.3%)
Q11	42(15.0%)	69(24.6%)	22(7.9%)	42(15.0%)	34(12.1%)	48(17.1%)	23(8.2%)
Q12	39(13.9%)	64(22.9%)	35(12.5%)	46(16.4%)	35(12.5%)	41(14.6%)	20(7.1%)
Q13	44(15.7%)	45(16.1%)	39(13.9%)	48(17.1%)	35(12.5%)	43(15.4%)	26(9.3%)
Q14	55(19.6%)	42(15.0%)	22(7.9%)	41(14.6%)	37(13.2%)	51(18.2%)	32(11.4%)
Q15	44(15.7%)	51(18.2%)	31(11.1%)	35(12.5%)	33(11.8%)	52(18.6%)	34(12.1%)
Q16	41(14.6%)	48(17.1%)	21(7.5%)	53(18.9%)	34(12.1%)	49(17.5%)	34(12.1%)

Table 3: OBSC score in frequency and percentage

Questions	SD	D	SWD	N	SWA	A	SA
Q17	57(20.4%)	35(12.5%)	23(8.2%)	38(13.6%)	29(10.4%)	65(23.2%)	33(11.8%)
Q18	52(18.6%)	35(12.5%)	26(9.3%)	39(13.9%)	26(9.3%)	68(24.3%)	34(12.1%)
Q19	57(20.4%)	38(13.6%)	28(10.0%)	23(8.2%)	33(11.8%)	63(22.5%)	38(13.6%)
Q20	55(19.6%)	42(15.0%)	27(9.6%)	26(9.3%)	38(13.6%)	63(22.5%)	29(10.4%)
Q21	53(18.9%)	39(13.9%)	23(8.2%)	31(11.1%)	45(16.1%)	54(19.6%)	35(12.5%)
Q22	54(19.3%)	47(16.8%)	26(9.3%)	39(13.9%)	34(12.1%)	48(17.1%)	32(11.4%)
Q23	47(16.8%)	52(18.6%)	26(9.3%)	34(12.1%)	35(12.5%)	59(21.1%)	27(9.6%)
Q24	87(31.1%)	31(11.1%)	25(8.9%)	20(7.1%)	30(10.7%)	57(20.4%)	30(10.7%)

Table 4: Total score of evaluate the relationship between OBSC and disciplines of the participants

OBSC SCALE	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS						
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	MEAN	MEDIAN	MODE	SE	SD
Low	7	2.5%	2.7143	3.0000	3.00	.03018	.50497
Moderate	66	23.6%					
High	207	73.9%					
OBSC SUB SCALE							
Surveillance	280	100%	33.98	32.000	24.0	.589	9.860
Body shame	280	100%	33.41	33.000	31.0	.606	10.153
Control belief	280	100%	32.82	32.000	33.0	.682	11.411
TOTAL	280	100.0					
INFERENCE STATISTICS							
Hypothesis	r	p. value	Hypothesis supported				
H1	-.124	.038	Yes				

DISCUSSION:

Regarding the Bio-demographical variables findings of this study, the mean age of participants was 21.60 ± 1.535 years, indicating that most of the students are belong to age group of 21 to 22 years. the majority of

participants were Muslims (90.4%), single (97.5%), and belonged to the middle socioeconomic class (84.6%). Slightly more than half of the students resided in rural areas (52.5%), while 47.5% were from urban settings. The students were almost equally distributed

across academic programs, including BS Nursing (25.71%), BS Public Health (25.36%), Doctor of Physiotherapy (25.00%), and Pharmacy-D (23.93%) which is associated with the OBCS. As per my findings the overall score of OBCS scale categorized into three levels and the results revealed a high level of objectified body consciousness level 73.9% moderate 23.6% and low 2.5% level. As the OBCS is a 24 items tool that was used to assess the degree to which a participants objectified their body and perceives themselves as a thing to be judged by others in the surroundings. The total mean of the score as per results of the participants 2.71 ± 0.50 . It has three subscales; Surveillance mean 33.98 indicate that high surveillance include how a person stays occupied with their body, performs body checking behaviors and looks at their body from an observer's perspective surveillance mean value specify high score indicate frequent body checking and a preoccupation with how one looks. The body shame mean 33.41 the high mean value specify the embarrassment a student feel for not fulfilling the ideal body standards, control belief score mean 32.82 this subscale explain the degree of perceived control a person has on her appearance, high mean indicate that students have a strong belief that their appearance can be controlled by putting efforts. A major finding of this study is the significant association between academic program and objectified body consciousness. Correlation analysis showed a statistically significant negative correlation ($r = -0.124$, $p = 0.038$), indicating that levels of objectified body consciousness varied across different academic disciplines. This finding suggests that educational context and program-specific environments may influence students' body related perceptions and monitoring of their bodies.

CONCLUSION:

Body image is a perception of how individual sees, think and feel their body appearance and Body consciousness plays a important role in developing self confidence, mental health and healthy lifestyle habits particularly among students. Finding concluded that there is a significant association between university programs and objectified body consciousness

level with negative correlation coefficient. It is also indicate that there is no association between other demographic information (Age, marital status, residence, academic year and socio-economic status of the students). Findings indicate that Majority of the students (73.9%) had high level of body consciousness while (23.6%) had moderate level of body consciousness level which lead to bad impact on students' perception about their body and lead to eating disorders, mental health imbalance and fear of judgment.

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